

Pseudocode of the Algorithms

This section presents all the algorithmic implementation of each pattern.

Rerouting related

Activity deviation [Algorithm 1](#).

Algorithm 1 Detect Activity Deviation

```
1: function DETECTACTIVITYDEVIATION( $l1, l2$ )
2:    $ResultsList \leftarrow \{\}$  ▷ Data structure to store flagged activities
3:   for each activity in  $l2$  do
4:      $ActivityDeviation \leftarrow \mathbf{True}$ 
5:     for each activity in  $l1$  do
6:       if ( $l2.activity == l1.activity$ ) then
7:          $ActivityDeviation \leftarrow \mathbf{False}$  ▷ Activity was found in model sample
8:         Break
9:       end if
10:    end for
11:    if ( $ActivityDeviation == \mathbf{True}$ ) then
12:       $ResultsList.append(l2.activity)$  ▷ Activity was not found in model sample
13:    end if
14:  end for
15:  return  $ResultsList$  ▷ Return flagged activities
16: end function
17:  $log \leftarrow logPath$  ▷ Assign log path
18:  $l1, l2 \leftarrow \text{SAMPLELOG}(log)$  ▷ Randomly sample the log into two segments
19: print DETECTACTIVITYDEVIATION( $l1, l2$ ) ▷ Call function, print out results
20: print DETECTACTIVITYDEVIATION( $l2, l1$ ) ▷ Swap roles of data segments and check again, print out results
```

Originator deviation [Algorithm 2](#)

Algorithm 2 Detect Originator Deviation

```
1: function DETECTORIGINATORDEVIATION(log, x, y)
2:   resultsList ← ▷ Data structure to store flagged activities and originators
3:   expectedOriginator ← ▷ Data structure to store the expected originators
4:   for k in x to y do
5:     l1, l2 ← SAMPLELOG(log, len(log) - k, k) ▷ Sample logs with size k
6:     if (k mod 2 == 0) then
7:       l1, l2 ← l2, l1 ▷ Swap samples if k is even
8:     end if
9:     for each activity in l1 do ▷ Learn assignment from l1
10:      expectedOriginator[activity] ← activity.resource
11:    end for
12:    for each activity in l2 do
13:      originatorDeviation ← False
14:      if (l2.activity.resource ≠ expectedOriginator[activity]) then
15:        originatorDeviation ← True ▷ Expected originator and actual originator are
different
16:      end if
17:      if (originatorDeviation == True) then
18:        resultsList.append(activity, l2.activity.resource, expectedOriginator[activity])
▷ Originator Deviation is detected, corresponding activity and resources added to results
19:      end if
20:    end for
21:  end for
22:  return resultsList ▷ Return flagged activities and originators
23: end function
24: log ← logPath ▷ Assign log path
25: x, y ← user defined values ▷ Define range for iterations and log sample size
26: print DETECTORIGINATORDEVIATION(log, x, y) ▷ Call function with user-defined range, print
out results
```

Reordering [Algorithm 3](#)

Algorithm 3 Detect Re-Ordering

```
1: function DETECTREORDERING(l1, l2)
2:   resultsList ← ▷ Data structure to store flagged cases
3:   activityOrders ← ▷ Data structure to store all possible activity orders
4:   for each case in l1 do
5:     activityOrders.append(l1.case.activities) ▷ Learn activity orders from l1
6:   end for
7:   for each case in l2 do
8:     reordering ← True
9:     if (l2.case.activities in activityOrders) then
10:      reordering ← False ▷ Order was found in model sample
11:     end if
12:     if (reordering == True) then
13:       resultsList.append(l2.case) ▷ Order was not found in model sample
14:     end if
15:   end for
16:   return resultsList ▷ Return flagged cases
17: end function
18: log ← logPath ▷ Assign log path
19: l1, l2 ← SAMPLECASES(log) ▷ Randomly sample the log into two segments containing complete
cases
20: print DETECTREORDERING(l1, l2) ▷ Call function, print out results
21: print DETECTREORDERING(l2, l1) ▷ Swap roles of data segments and check again, print out
results
```

Preferential work selection [Algorithm 4](#)

Algorithm 4 Detect Preferential Work Selection

```
1: function DETECTPREFERENTIALWORKSELECTIONAVERAGE(log)
2:   resultsList ←  $\emptyset$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store flagged activities and resources
3:   activityFrequency ←  $\emptyset$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store the frequency of each activity for each
   resource
4:   averageFrequency ←  $\emptyset$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store the average frequency of each activity
5:   for each event in the log do
6:     activityFrequency[event.activity][event.resource] += 1  $\triangleright$  Count frequency of each
   activity for each resource
7:   end for
8:   for each activity in activityFrequency do
9:     averageFrequency[activity] ← activityFrequency[activity].mean()  $\triangleright$  Calculate
   average frequency
10:    for each resource do
11:      if (activityFrequency[activity][resource] - averageFrequency[activity] >
   threshold) then
12:        resultsList.append(activity, resource)  $\triangleright$  The resource chose the activity more
   frequently than expected
13:      end if
14:    end for
15:  end for
16:  return resultsList  $\triangleright$  Return flagged activities and resources
17: end function
18: function DETECTPREFERENTIALWORKSELECTIONFCFS(log)
19:   resultsList ←  $\emptyset$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store flagged activities, cases and resources
20:   for each event with start and complete timestamps in the log do
21:     startTimestamp ← event.startTimestamp
22:     completeTimestamp ← event.completeTimestamp
23:     for each other event by the same resource in a different case do
24:       if (otherEvent.startTimestamp > startTimestamp  $\wedge$ 
   otherEvent.startTimestamp < completeTimestamp) then
25:         resultsList.append(otherEvent.activity, otherEvent.case, otherEvent.resource)
    $\triangleright$  New activity was started in another case while the resource was not finished
26:       end if
27:     end for
28:   end for
29:   return resultsList  $\triangleright$  Return flagged activities, cases and resources
30: end function
31: log ← logPath  $\triangleright$  Assign log path
32: print DETECTPREFERENTIALWORKSELECTIONAVERAGE(log)  $\triangleright$  Call function to detect the
   pattern based on average frequency, print out results
33: print DETECTPREFERENTIALWORKSELECTIONFCFS(log)  $\triangleright$  Call function to detect the pattern
   based on an unexpected case order, print out results
```

Performance related

Performance masking [Algorithm 5](#)

Algorithm 5 Detect Performance Masking

```
1: function DETECTPERFORMANCEMASKING(log)
2:   resultsList ←  $\{\}$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store flagged resources, activities and cases
3:   casesManyEvents ←  $\{\}$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store cases with many events
4:   for each case in the log do
5:     eventCount ← 0
6:     for each event in the case do
7:       eventCount += 1
8:     end for
9:     if (eventCount > threshold1) then
10:      casesManyEvents.append(case)  $\triangleright$  Store cases with many events
11:    end if
12:  end for
13:  for each case in casesManyEvents do
14:    frequentActivities ←  $\{\}$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store frequent activities
15:    activityCount ←  $\{\}$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store count of each activity
16:    for each event in the case do
17:      activityCount[event.activity] += 1  $\triangleright$  Count occurrences of each activity
18:      if (activityCount[event.activity] > threshold2) then
19:        frequentActivities.append(event)  $\triangleright$  Store frequently occurring activities
20:      end if
21:    end for
22:    for each event in frequentActivities do
23:      if (event.duration < threshold3) then
24:        resultsList.append(event.resource, event.activity, event.case)  $\triangleright$  In a case with
many events, activities occurred very often in a short amount of time
25:      end if
26:    end for
27:  end for
28:  return resultsList  $\triangleright$  Return flagged resources, activities and cases
29: end function
30: log ← logPath  $\triangleright$  Assign log path
31: print DETECTPERFORMANCEMASKING(log)  $\triangleright$  Call function, print out results
```

Performance blow out [Algorithm 6](#)

Algorithm 6 Detect Performance Blow-Out

```
1: function DETECTPERFORMANCEBLOWOUT(log)
2:   resultsList ←  $\{\}$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store flagged resources and activities
3:   completionTimes ←  $\{\}$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store completion times
4:   for each event in the log do
5:     completionTimes[event.activity][event.resource].append(event.duration)
6:     if (len(completionTimes[event.activity][event.resource]) > 1) then  $\triangleright$  If the activity
was conducted more than once, check for a time increase
7:       for n in range len(completionTimes[event.activity][event.resource]) do
8:         if (completionTimes[event.activity][event.resource][n] >
completionTimes[event.activity][event.resource][n-1] + threshold1) then  $\triangleright$ 
9:           ResultsList.append(event.resource, event.activity)  $\triangleright$  The resource got slower
over time conducting the same activity
10:        end if
11:      end for
12:    end if
13:  end for
14:  for each activity in completionTimes do
15:    standardDeviation ← completionTimes[activity].mean().standardDeviation()  $\triangleright$ 
Calculate standard deviation for each activity
16:    if (standardDeviation > threshold2) then
17:      ResultsList.append(activity)  $\triangleright$  Different resources needed very different times to
conduct the activity
18:    end if
19:  end for
20:  return resultsList  $\triangleright$  Return flagged resources and activities
21: end function
22: log ← logPath  $\triangleright$  Assign log path
23: print DETECTPERFORMANCEBLOWOUT(log)  $\triangleright$  Call function, print out results
```

Overwork hiding [Algorithm 7](#)

Algorithm 7 Detect Overwork Hiding

```
1: function DETECTOVERWORKHIDING(log)
2:   resultsList ← ▷ Data structure to store flagged activities, cases and resources
3:   workStartTimes ← ▷ Data structure to store the starting times of work for each resource,
   should get a default value for each resource without a manual entry
4:   workEndTimes ← ▷ Data structure to store the ending times of work for each resource,
   should get a default value for each resource without a manual entry
5:   for each event in the log do
6:     if (event.startTimestamp < workStartTimes[event.resource]) then
7:       resultsList.append(event.activity, event.case, event.resource) ▷ Work was
   conducted before working time started
8:     end if
9:     if (event.completeTimestamp > workEndTimes[event.resource]) then
10:      resultsList.append(event.activity, event.case, event.resource) ▷ Work was
   conducted after working time ended
11:    end if
12:  end for
13:  return resultsList ▷ Return flagged activities, cases and resources
14: end function
15: log ← logPath ▷ Assign log path
16: print DETECTOVERWORKHIDING(log) ▷ Call function, print out results
```

Gold plating [Algorithm 8](#)

Algorithm 8 Detect Gold Plating

```
1: function CATEGORIZEPROCESSVARIANTS(log)
2:   processVariants ← ▷ Data structure to store all process variants
3:   for each case in the log do
4:     if (case.activities ∉ processVariants) then
5:       processVariants.append(case) ▷ Store unique process variants
6:     end if
7:   end for
8:   return processVariants ▷ Return all process variants
9: end function
10: function DETECTGOLDPLATINGDURATION(log, processVariants)
11:   resultsList ← ▷ Data structure to store flagged cases
12:   overallAverageVariantAverage ← processVariants.case.duration.mean() ▷ Calculate overall average case duration
13:   for each variant in processVariants do
14:     variantAverageDuration ← variant.case.duration.mean() ▷ Calculate average case duration for variant
15:     if (variantAverageDuration − overallAverageVariantAverage > threshold1) then
16:       resultsList.append(variant.cases) ▷ Variant takes significantly longer to complete on average than expected
17:     end if
18:   end for
19:   return resultsList ▷ Return flagged cases
20: end function
21: function DETECTGOLDPLATINGRARE(log, processVariants)
22:   resultsList ← ▷ Data structure to store flagged activities and variants
23:   activityFrequencies ← ▷ Data structure to store frequency of each activity
24:   activitiesOccurrences ← ▷ Data structure to store variants in which each activity occurs
25:   for each variant in processVariants do
26:     for each event in the variant do
27:       activityFrequencies[event.activity] + = 1 ▷ Count frequency of activity
28:       activitiesOccurrences[event.activity].append(variant) ▷ Track variants in which activity occurs
29:     end for
30:   end for
31:   for each activity in activityFrequencies do
32:     if (activityFrequencies[activity] > threshold2) then
33:       for each variant in activitiesOccurrences[activity] do
34:         resultsList.append(activity, variant) ▷ The variant contains a significantly rare activity
35:       end for
36:     end if
37:   end for
38:   return resultsList ▷ Return flagged activities and variants
39: end function
40: log ← logPath ▷ Assign log path
41: processVariants ← CATEGORIZEPROCESSVARIANTS(log) ▷ Call function to categorize process variants
42: print DETECTGOLDPLATINGDURATION(log, processVariants) ▷ Call function to detect the pattern based on completion times, print out results
43: print DETECTGOLDPLATINGRARE(log, processVariants) ▷ Call function to detect the pattern based on significantly rare activities, print out results
```

Social related

Idling [Algorithm 9](#)

Algorithm 9 Detect Idling

```
1: function DETECTIDLINGAVERAGE(log)
2:   resultsList ←  $\triangleright$  Data structure to store flagged resources and activities
3:   completionTimes ←  $\triangleright$  Data structure to store completion times of each resource for each
   activity
4:   activityCount ←  $\triangleright$  Data structure to store how often each activity was conducted by each
   resource
5:   totalCompletionTimes ←  $\triangleright$  Data structure to store total completion times of each activity
6:   resourceAverageTimes ←  $\triangleright$  Data structure to store average times for each resource
7:   averageOfAverageTimes ←  $\triangleright$  Data structure to store average of average times for each
   resource
8:   for each event in the log do
9:     completionTimes[event.activity][event.resource] += event.duration  $\triangleright$  Sum
   completion times
10:    activityCount[event.activity][event.resource] += 1  $\triangleright$  Count occurrences
11:  end for
12:  for each activity in completionTimes do
13:    totalCompletionTimes[activity] =  $\sum(\text{completionTimes}[\text{activity}])$   $\triangleright$  Calculate total
   completion times
14:    for each resource in completionTimes[activity] do
15:       $\text{averageTime} = \frac{\text{completionTimes}[\text{activity}][\text{resource}]}{\text{activityCount}[\text{activity}][\text{resource}]}$ 
16:       $\text{totalAverageTime} = \frac{\text{totalCompletionTimes}[\text{activity}]}{\sum(\text{activityCount}[\text{activity}])}$ 
17:      if (averageTime – totalAverageTime > threshold1) then
18:        resultsList.append(resource, activity)  $\triangleright$  The resource needed significantly more
   time for the activity than other resources
19:      end if
20:      resourceAverageTimes[resource].append(averageTime)  $\triangleright$  Store average
21:    end for
22:  end for
23:  for each resource in resourceAverageTimes do
24:     $\text{averageOfAverageTimes}[\text{resource}] = \frac{\sum(\text{resourceAverageTimes}[\text{resource}])}{\text{len}(\text{resourceAverageTimes}[\text{resource}])}$ 
25:  end for
26:  for each activity in completionTimes do
27:    for each resource in completionTimes[activity] do
28:       $\text{averageTime} = \frac{\text{completionTimes}[\text{activity}][\text{resource}]}{\text{activityCount}[\text{activity}][\text{resource}]}$ 
29:      if (averageTime – averageOfAverageTimes[resource] > threshold2) then
30:        resultsList.append(resource, activity)  $\triangleright$  The resource needed significantly more
   time for the activity than for other activities
31:      end if
32:    end for
33:  end for
34:  return resultsList  $\triangleright$  Return flagged resources and activities
35: end function
36: function DETECTIDLINGBREAK(log)
37:   resultsList ←  $\triangleright$  Data structure to store flagged resources, activities and cases
38:   lastCompleteTimestamp ←  $\triangleright$  Data structure to store last complete timestamps for each
   resource
39:   for each event in the log assigned to the resource do
40:     if (event.lifecycle == complete) then
41:       lastCompleteTimestamp[event.resource] = event.timestamp  $\triangleright$  Store last
   complete timestamp
42:     else
43:       timeDifference = event.timestamp – lastCompleteTimestamp[event.resource]
44:       if (timeDifference > threshold) then
45:         resultsList.append(event.resource, event.activity, event.case)  $\triangleright$  The resource
   took a significantly long break here
46:       end if
47:     end if
48:   end for
49:   return resultsList  $\triangleright$  Return flagged resources, activities and cases
50: end function
51: log ← logPath  $\triangleright$  Assign log path
52: print DETECTIDLINGAVERAGE(logs)  $\triangleright$  Call function to detect the pattern based on average
   completion times, print out results
53: print DETECTIDLINGBREAK(log, processVariants)  $\triangleright$  Call function to detect the pattern based
   on significantly long breaks, print out results
```

Social loafing [Algorithm 10](#)

Algorithm 10 Detect Social Loafing

```
1: function ADDGROUPWORKFLAG(log)
2:   log[groupWorkFlag]  $\leftarrow$  False  $\triangleright$  Initialize group work flag
3:   resourceEventCount  $\leftarrow$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store the count of events by each resource in
   each case
4:   for each case in the log do
5:     for each event in the case do
6:       resourceEventCount[case][event.resource] += 1  $\triangleright$  Count events by each resource
7:       for each other event in the case do
8:         if (event.resource  $\neq$  otherEvent.resource  $\wedge$  event.startTimestamp  $\leq$ 
           otherEvent.completeTimestamp  $\wedge$  event.completeTimestamp  $\geq$ 
           otherEvent.startTimestamp) then
9:           event.groupWorkFlag  $\leftarrow$  True  $\triangleright$  Flag overlapping events from different
           resources
10:          otherEvent.groupWorkFlag  $\leftarrow$  True
11:        end if
12:        if (event.resource  $\neq$  otherEvent.resource  $\wedge$  event.activity ==
           otherEvent.activity) then
13:          event.groupWorkFlag  $\leftarrow$  True  $\triangleright$  Flag events with the same activity from
           different resources
14:          otherEvent.groupWorkFlag  $\leftarrow$  True
15:        end if
16:      end for
17:    end for
18:    for each resource do
19:      for each other resource do
20:        overlaps  $\leftarrow$  0
21:        overlappingEvents  $\leftarrow$ 
22:        if (resourceEventCount[case][resource]  $\geq$  10  $\wedge$ 
           resourceEventCount[case][otherResource]  $\geq$  10) then
23:          case.groupWorkFlag  $\leftarrow$  True  $\triangleright$  Flag events where multiple resources
           registered at least 10 events in a case
24:        end if
25:        for each event of the two resources do
26:          if (resource.event.timestamp  $\leq$  otherResource.event.timestamp +
           10 minutes) then
27:            overlaps += 1
28:            overlappingEvents.append(resource.event, otherResource.event)
29:          end if
30:          if (overlaps  $\geq$  3) then
31:            resource.event.groupWorkFlag  $\leftarrow$  True  $\triangleright$  Flag events with multiple
           resources registering events within 10 minutes at least three times in a case
32:            otherResource.event.groupWorkFlag  $\leftarrow$  True
33:          end if
34:        end for
35:      end for
36:    end for
37:    return log  $\triangleright$  Return log with added group work flag attribute
38:  end function
39: function DETECTSOCIALLOAFING(log)
40:   resultsList  $\leftarrow$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store flagged resources and completion times
41:   for each resource do
42:     totalGroupWorkTime  $\leftarrow$  0
43:     totalIndividualWorkTime  $\leftarrow$  0
44:     totalGroupWorkEvents  $\leftarrow$  0
45:     totalIndividualWorkEvents  $\leftarrow$  0
46:     for each event registered by the resource do
47:       if (event.groupWorkFlag  $\leftarrow$  True) then
48:         totalGroupWorkTime += event.duration
49:         totalGroupWorkEvents += 1
50:       else
51:         totalIndividualWorkTime += event.duration
52:         totalIndividualWorkEvents += 1
53:       end if
54:     end for
55:     avgGroupEventTime  $\leftarrow$   $\frac{\textit{totalGroupWorkTime}}{\textit{totalGroupWorkEvents}}$ 
56:     avgIndividualEventTime  $\leftarrow$   $\frac{\textit{totalIndividualWorkTime}}{\textit{totalIndividualWorkEvents}}$ 
57:     if (avgGroupEventTime - avgIndividualEventTime > threshold) then
58:       resultsList.append(resource, avgGroupEventTime, avgIndividualEventTime)  $\triangleright$ 
59:       The resource works significantly slower on average during group work
60:     end if
61:   end for
62:   return resultsList  $\triangleright$  Return flagged resources and completion times
63: end function
64: log  $\leftarrow$  logPath  $\triangleright$  Assign log path
65: log  $\leftarrow$  ADDGROUPWORKFLAG(log)  $\triangleright$  Call function to add group work flag
66: print DETECTSOCIALLOAFING(log)  $\triangleright$  Call function, print out results
```

Peer mobbing [Algorithm 11](#)

Algorithm 11 Detect Peer Mobbing

```

1: function DETECTPEERMOBBING(log)
2:   resultsList ←      ▷ Data structure to store flagged resources and potentially mobbing
   resources
3:   activityFrequency ← ▷ Data structure to store frequency of each activity being conducted
   by each resource
4:   averageFrequency ← ▷ Data structure to store average frequency of each activity being
   conducted
5:   for each resource do
6:     for each activity performed by the resource do
7:       activityFrequency[event.activity][resource] += 1  ▷ Calculate frequency of each
   activity conducted by each resource
8:     end for
9:   end for
10:  for each activity do
11:    averageFrequency[activity] ← mean(activityFrequency[activity])      ▷ Calculate
   average frequency of each activity
12:    for each resource do
13:      victimDeviation ←      activityFrequency[activity][resource] -
   averageFrequency[activity]
14:    mobbingResources ←      ▷ Data structure for list of resources taking part in Peer
   Mobbing
15:    for each other resource do
16:      mobbingDeviation ←      activityFrequency[activity][otherResource] -
   averageFrequency[activity]
17:      if (mobbingDeviation > victimDeviation + threshold1) then
18:        mobbingResources.append(otherResource)      ▷ Flag resource conducting
   activity significantly more often
19:      end if
20:    end for
21:    if (len(mobbingResources) > threshold2) then
22:      resultsList.append(resource, mobbingResources)      ▷ Significantly many
   resources were flagged for having conducted an activity significantly more often than a single
   resource
23:    end if
24:  end for
25:  end for
26:  return resultsList      ▷ Return flagged resources and potentially mobbing resources
27: end function
28: log ← logPath      ▷ Assign log path
29: print DETECTPEERMOBBING(log)      ▷ Call function, print out results

```

Boss mobbing [Algorithm 12](#)

Algorithm 12 Detect Boss Mobbing

```
1: function ADDGROUPWORKFLAG(log)
2:   [...]  $\triangleright$  Same function used for the detection of Social Loafing
3: end function
4: function DETECTBOSSMOBBING(log, bossTakeoverTimestamp)
5:   resultsList  $\leftarrow$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store flagged resources
6:   eventsBeforeBoss  $\leftarrow$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store group events before boss takeover
7:   eventsAfterBoss  $\leftarrow$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store group events after boss takeover
8:   for each event with groupWorkFlag  $\leftarrow$  True do
9:     if (event.timestamp < bossTakeoverTimestamp) then
10:      eventsBeforeBoss.append(event)
11:     end if
12:     if (event.timestamp  $\geq$  bossTakeoverTimestamp) then
13:      eventsAfterBoss.append(event)
14:     end if
15:   end for
16:   avgDurationBefore  $\leftarrow$  eventsBeforeBoss.duration.mean()  $\triangleright$  Calculate average group
   completion times before boss takeover
17:   avgDurationAfter  $\leftarrow$  eventsAfterBoss.duration.mean()  $\triangleright$  Calculate average group
   completion times after boss takeover
18:   for each resource do
19:     if (avgDurationAfter[resource] - avgDurationBefore[resource] > threshold) then
20:       resultsList.append(resource)  $\triangleright$  The resource performed significantly better in
   group work before boss takeover
21:     end if
22:   end for
23:   return resultsList  $\triangleright$  Return flagged resources
24: end function
25: log  $\leftarrow$  logPath  $\triangleright$  Assign log path
26: log  $\leftarrow$  AddGroupWorkFlag(log)  $\triangleright$  Call function to add group work flag
27: bossTakeoverTimestamp  $\leftarrow$  Timestamp  $\triangleright$  Assign boss takeover timestamp
28: print DETECTBOSSMOBBING(log, bossTakeoverTimestamp)  $\triangleright$  Call function, print out results
```

Social borrowing [Algorithm 13](#)

Algorithm 13 Detect Social Borrowing

```
1: function DETECTSOCIALBORROWING(log)
2:   resultsList  $\leftarrow$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store flagged resources
3:   workStartTimes  $\leftarrow$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store the starting times of work
4:   workEndTimes  $\leftarrow$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store the ending times of work
5:   overlapCompletionTimes  $\leftarrow$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store the completion times while
   resources work together
6:   aloneCompletionTimes  $\leftarrow$   $\triangleright$  Data structure to store the completion times while resources
   work alone
7:   for each resource not in workStartTimes do
8:     for each event of the resource do
9:       workStartTimes[resource]  $\leftarrow$   $\min(\text{event.timestamp}, \text{workStartTimes}[\text{resource}])$ 
10:    end for
11:  end for
12:  for each resource not in workEndTimes do
13:    for each event of the resource do
14:      workEndTimes[resource]  $\leftarrow$   $\max(\text{event.timestamp}, \text{workEndTimes}[\text{resource}])$ 
15:    end for
16:  end for
17:  for each resource do
18:    for each other resource do
19:      if (workStartTimes[resource] > workEndTimes[otherResource] then
   or workStartTimes[otherResource] > workEndTimes[resource])
20:        Break
21:      else
22:        overlapStart  $\leftarrow$   $\max(\text{workStartTimes}[\text{resource}], \text{workStartTimes}[\text{otherResource}])$ 
 $\triangleright$  Calculate time interval where the working times of the resources overlap
23:        overlapEnd  $\leftarrow$   $\min(\text{workEndTimes}[\text{resource}], \text{workEndTimes}[\text{otherResource}])$ 
24:        for each event of the first resource during overlapStart and overlapEnd do
25:          overlapCompletionTimes[resource].append(event.duration)  $\triangleright$  Calculate
   completion times during overlap
26:        end for
27:        for each event of the first resource outside of overlapStart and overlapEnd do
28:          aloneCompletionTimes[resource].append(event.duration)  $\triangleright$  Calculate
   completion times outside overlap
29:        end for
30:        for each event of the other resource during overlapStart and overlapEnd do
31:          overlapCompletionTimes[otherResource].append(event.duration)
32:        end for
33:        for each event of the other resource outside of overlapStart and overlapEnd do
34:          aloneCompletionTimes[otherResource].append(event.duration)
35:        end for
36:        if (overlapCompletionTimes[resource].mean() -
   aloneCompletionTimes[resource].mean() > threshold
   and aloneCompletionTimes[otherResource].mean()  $\leq$ 
   overlapCompletionTimes[otherResource].mean()) then
37:          resultsList.append(resource, otherResource)  $\triangleright$  Flag resources with
   correlated performance
38:        end if
39:      end if
40:    end for
41:  end for
42:  return resultsList  $\triangleright$  Return flagged resources
43: end function
44: log  $\leftarrow$  DetectSocialBorrowing  $\triangleright$  Assign log path
45: print DETECTSOCIALBORROWING(log)  $\triangleright$  Call function, print out results
```
